

Kangaroo Care for low-birth-weight babies

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RECOMMENDED

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Ambitious Impact (AIM) exists to increase the number and quality of effective charities improving human and animal well-being worldwide. We strive to achieve this goal through our rigorous research process and our Incubator Program, which connects talented individuals with high-impact ideas.

Our **Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program** provides potential entrepreneurs with two months of cost-covered, intensive training designed by founders for founders, along with ongoing support. Our researchers identify evidence-based, high-impact interventions and guide founders in finding co-founders to launch and scale these ideas.

Note to readers: Our research is designed for AIM decision-makers and Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program participants. It aims to identify the best ideas for our programs. Consequently, reports on those not recommended for incubation can often be less polished.

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Scaling up Kangaroo Care / Summary

Description

This report is an update on our previous research on Kangaroo Care (KC). KC is a package of interventions which involves skin-to-skin contact between a low birth weight baby and a caregiver, exclusive breastfeeding, and close monitoring of the baby and their relevant vital and danger signs. KC is a cheap and easy-to-administer form of neonatal care that is evidenced to be effective at reducing mortality and morbidity. AIM has incubated one KC-providing organization working in India, Ansh (launched in early 2023; see original report [here](#)).

Counterfactual impact

Cost-effectiveness analysis: We updated our 2022 cost-effectiveness analysis using our new template, incorporating data from Ansh's pilot¹ and revised effect sizes for KC's impact on mortality and morbidity based on our updated evidence review. Embedding KC capacity in hospitals in Pakistan is expected to be highly cost-effective, surpassing the cost-effectiveness anticipated by our previous model (see comparison [here](#)). The updated model estimates that the intervention could avert one DALY for every \$50 spent (see [CEA](#) and [discussion](#)).

Potential for success

Robustness of evidence: Overall, we are encouraged by the early-stage success of Ansh in building strong relationships with key stakeholders, which we feel is necessary for success in this space. Despite this update to feasibility, Ansh's pilot shows that not all parents reach 8 hours of daily skin-to-skin contact. This may decrease the effectiveness of KC, as our understanding of its effects is largely based on evidence of 8 or more hours per day. Considering these factors and new evidence since publication, we have slightly reduced our estimate of KC's mortality effects, but slightly increased our estimate of its morbidity effects (see [here](#)).

¹ Our CEA relies on pilot data from work in two hospitals in Rajasthan from January to March 2024, but Ansh is now in their scale-up phase so specific numbers used in this model could already be out of date.

Theory of Change: We still think embedding capacity into the health system is a strong ToC that addresses many barriers to scaling up KC. We also weakly endorse exploring context-specific alternative ToCs, in particular, [KC for emergency transport](#) and initiating [KC outside hospital settings](#) (see [here](#)).

Neglectedness

Geographic assessment: KC still remains highly neglected. We updated our assessment using a new template and more recent data. The recommended target countries remain largely the same, with most shifting positions within the top 10 (see [model](#) and [discussion](#)).

Other

Expert views: We spoke with Ansh, GiveWell, and another KC implementation org whose insights mostly gave us positive updates, particularly regarding the value of starting an organization sooner rather than later.

Implementation factors: It would benefit the founding team to have a healthcare/medical background and familiarity with the target country, either through being a local or having previous work experience. We think a local founder would be preferable to make stakeholder relationships and access easier.

Scaling up Kangaroo Care / Crucial considerations

Is it too early to recommend a non-profit organization again on the same idea?

It is still too early to determine whether Ansh has been a success (though we are encouraged by its early progress). Success, in our view, requires both organizational sustainability and the intervention achieving scale and cost-effectiveness—aspects that take time and are difficult to evaluate. Therefore, we do not think that Ansh’s promising progress should heavily influence our stance on recommending the idea again.

However, we believe two key factors should shape our decision-making:

1. Even if Ansh continues on a positive path, KC is sufficiently highly neglected across many geographies, creating opportunities for a new organization to support healthcare outcomes elsewhere. If Ansh continues to grow, it will expand within Rajasthan and into other Indian states.
2. We consider KC to be a highly evidenced and robust intervention. If deployed with fidelity and in line with best practices, we have high expectations that it will support positive healthcare outcomes.

Should we be concerned about intervention fidelity and quality?

We note with some concern that data from Ansh’s pilot found an average skin-to-skin contact duration below the best practice recommendation of 8 hours whilst caregivers and babies are still on the ward (note that the duration of skin-to-skin contact on the ward has improved since the pilot and, again based on the pilot, that 70% of parents manage to reach this minimum duration once they are at home). Overall, this is a soft negative update, which we expect could slightly reduce true effectiveness and cost-effectiveness, though both are still likely to remain high. This highlights the importance of monitoring and evaluation to determine fidelity to KC best practices and the potential trade-offs between higher scale, lower-cost and lower-intensity models and fidelity.

What type of talent should run this intervention?

In line with the philosophy of the Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program (CEIP), we do not believe that any specific backgrounds are needed, as various potential backgrounds would bring their own benefits and drawbacks. It would benefit the founding team to have a healthcare/medical background and familiarity with the target country, either through being a local or having previous work experience. A local founder would maximize the chances of stakeholder relationships going well—which is the key component of this intervention—as stakeholders often want to speak to the organization's leaders. It would be a great benefit to be able to speak the language, understand the local context, and not be seen as an outsider.

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1 Background

Ambitious Impact (AIM) exists to increase the number and quality of effective non-profits working to improve human and animal wellbeing. AIM connects talented individuals with high-impact ideas by providing potential entrepreneurs with intensive training and ongoing support to launch and scale these ideas. Our research team focuses on identifying impactful opportunities.

As part of our 2024 research agenda, we reviewed past recommendations to determine whether any should be re-issued to new founders. In this context, we revisited our recommendation on scaling up Kangaroo Care (KC) for low birth weight (LBW) babies ([Fairless, 2023](#)).² This report updates our original findings and is intended to be read as a companion to it.

² We use the term "Kangaroo Care" (KC) instead of the more commonly used "Kangaroo Mother Care" (KMC) to avoid the use of gendered language and to acknowledge that caregivers other than mothers can participate in KC.

2 Theories of Change

We revisited our review of potential theories of change (ToCs) to assess whether our recommendation to potential founders in this space should change. We still think [embedding capacity](#) into the health system is a strong ToC, addressing many identified barriers to scaling up KC. Potential co-founders could also investigate ToCs that include [KC for emergency transport](#) and initiating [KC outside hospital settings](#). While these two ToCs generally have weaker supporting evidence, we think they are worth exploring for specific settings and where testing them could advance standard procedure quality for other providers.

2.1 Defining KC as an intervention

KC is a cheap and easy-to-administer package of neonatal care interventions which involves skin-to-skin contact between the baby and a caregiver, exclusive breastfeeding, and close monitoring of the baby and relevant vital and danger signs.

We think that all components of KC are equally important, and though we focus more on skin-to-skin contact in this report and how its duration impacts the fidelity of KC (see [Section 4.3](#)), we do not think that this is the most critical component of the package and recommend founders equally focus on the breastfeeding and close monitoring components of this intervention. Indeed, Supriya suggested that monitoring babies for danger signs (such as symptoms of acute respiratory distress so parents know when to return to the hospital for emergency care) may be the component that contributes most to the mortality reductions Ansh has seen.

2.2 Embedding capacity in the health system

Our previous report recommended a specific ToC that involved embedding capacity to increase KC adoption directly within hospitals ([Fairless, 2023](#)). This approach involves adding human resources, technical expertise, and inputs for KC into existing hospitals. This could include, for example, establishing a dedicated KC

ward or adding KC capacity to existing neonatal/maternal wards, staffed and managed by the nonprofit.

The report led to the creation of [Ansh](#), which later adapted the ToC by implementing a lighter-touch approach. Instead of establishing dedicated KC wards, they embed into existing hospital maternity sections by equipping them with necessary items like KC chairs, KC wraps, and weighing scales. They also provide each hospital with a dedicated team consisting of a program coordinator, a monitoring and evaluation (M&E) coordinator, and 11–12 skilled nurses who receive a 3-day training to ensure proficiency in KC practices. To ensure continued KC following discharge, they also conduct four weekly follow-up phone calls until the baby reaches one month of age ([Bansal, 2024](#)).

We still believe the embedding capacity model is a promising focus for a new charity. This approach is well suited to low-resource and high-burden contexts, where common barriers to KC scale-up include resource shortages. We speculate that prioritizing sustainability—eventually transitioning operational ownership to hospitals or public health providers—could enhance the organization's cost-effectiveness.

2.3 Training and technical assistance

Training and technical assistance are among the most common ToCs currently being implemented by other organizations working on KC. Based on our review of organization websites and discussions with experts, training is typically provided by a center of excellence or a nonprofit organization, either through training trainers or directly training practitioners.

We ruled out this ToC in our original report and still broadly agree with our reasoning for doing so. It does not seem like the most promising ToC for a new organization to implement, as its scale seems capped by the number of hospitals and nonprofit organizations interested in attending the training. Moreover, even if many hospitals and nonprofit organizations receive the training, large-scale implementation of KC is still likely to fail due to insufficient post-training support, limited resources, faltering political will, or opposition to KC. Adding more layers

between the primary trainer and the implementation area makes it harder to maintain fidelity to the training.

We still believe this ToC could work well with extensive buy-in, embedded collaboration, and sufficient resources, but these conditions are unlikely to be found in our target countries. If we think it could be promising, it may be worth exploring this ToC in the future using wards where a new charity has embedded capacity as a center of excellence.

2.4 Community initiation through health workers

Community initiation of KC relies on Community Health Workers (CHWs) identifying LBW neonates in the community who have not received appropriate care and coaching their caregivers in providing it. **We expect that community-based KC has a similar effect size as facility-based KC.** In fact, the impact per LBW neonate may be larger for community-based KC, as the counterfactual care in the community is likely to be worse than counterfactual care in a facility. That said, we expect there are hospitals where the counterfactual care means no care, and think that targeting these hospitals where possible would be valuable.

However, overall, we are less enthusiastic about community initiation as an approach, as it has a weaker evidence base compared to facility-based KC.

There are no existing organizations working on this, and only two studies estimate its mortality outcomes ([Mazumder et al., 2019](#); [Sloan et al., 2008](#)). Additionally, we expect community initiation of KC to be more expensive per neonate, as identifying these babies may prove challenging.

We think that community-based KC could be more appropriate in the following scenarios:

- Hospitals are operating beyond capacity, making it impossible to embed KC due to space constraints.
- The rate of births in facilities is generally low.

- Community health worker platforms are already robust and the primary form of care, e.g., in countries where most antenatal care is provided by community health workers.

2.5 Kangaroo care for (emergency) transport

An expert expressed interest in increasing the use of KC during (mostly emergency) transport. Many newborn transport units lack transport incubators, resulting in high neonatal mortality during transport ([Nimbalkar et al., 2023](#)).³ KC could serve as a simple and effective alternative in resource-limited settings where such equipment is unavailable. The expert was keen to see KC being used more in transport, as this is often a neglected focus area in existing KC programs.

Ensuring that KC is given to neonates in transport may reduce risks associated with transportation. While the evidence supporting this practice is preliminary, it warrants further exploration. A small randomized controlled trial (RCT) conducted in India with 152 LBW neonates found that “low birth weight neonates receiving KMC showed optimal thermoregulation, whereas a high incidence of moderate hypothermia was seen among neonates receiving conventional care during transport” ([Nimbalkar et al., 2023, p.1](#)). Moreover, KC during transport may be preferable to incubator care, which carries risks such as instability during transport (leading to increased mortality and morbidity), inadequate systems to secure the infant in the event of an accident, and the separation of mother and infant ([Sontheimer, Fischer & Buch, 2004](#)).

A non-profit could support improvements in neonatal transportation by conducting primary research on KC for transport. We ruled this out as a standalone ToC due to its weaker evidence base compared to standard KC. If a new charity focused on KC wants to support improvements in neonatal transportation, it could experiment with adding a KC transport component to the existing training provided to nurses and parents. This addition might be worth considering once standard KC is established, serving as a promising experiment to

³ Note that both the linked study and the expert's comments focused on India. It is unclear whether this issue is as significant or should be prioritized in other regions.

help strengthen the evidence base for KC in transport, given the current scarcity of evidence.

2.6 Conclusion

We are enthusiastic about the potential for another new charity pursuing the embedding capacity model, as it continues to stand out as the most solid ToC.

We think this could include a specific focus on transport KC where relevant. While community-based KC also shows promise, it would require prioritizing different factors than the embedding capacity approach, such as higher rates of births outside facilities or hospitals lacking capacity for embedding KC. As we are more excited about the embedding capacity approach, community-based KC falls outside the scope of this report.

3 Updated geographic assessment

We updated our 2022 geographic assessment using a new template and more recent data on the prevalence and number of LBW babies per country, the burden of neonatal disorders, and tractability indicators and indexes. This [new geographic assessment](#) was conducted to evaluate whether our recommended target countries for a new charity should change. Overall, the recommended target countries remain largely the same, with most shifting positions within the top 10. This updated assessment suggests that a new KC scale-up charity could prioritize work in Pakistan, Nigeria, Niger, Guinea-Bissau, Angola, Guinea, Côte d'Ivoire, Lesotho, Madagascar, or Benin.

Among the prioritized countries in our [revised geographic assessment](#), Pakistan stands out as particularly promising. Within Pakistan, key states to consider focusing on include Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Balochistan, and Azad Jammu & Kashmir.

We updated our old geographic assessment by:

- Using our new template.
- Ruling out countries where the neonatal mortality rate is less than 10 per 1,000 live births, or where implementation would be extremely difficult (e.g., Somalia).
- We also ruled out India as a target country as Ansh is working and plans to scale there. Ansh ran its pilot in two hospitals in Rajasthan from January to March 2024 and is now scaling up in Rajasthan. It will scale to other states in India over time.
- Incorporating more recent data published since the original report, namely: 2020 data on the prevalence and number of LBW babies per country from [Okwaraji et al. \(2024\)](#); 2021 Global Burden of Disease (GBD) data on the DALY burden of neonatal disorders; and 2023/4 updates to our tractability indicators and indexes.
- Including sub-national level data, where available and appropriate, for large countries like India, Pakistan, and Ethiopia to provide a more granular assessment.

We hoped to include data on existing KC coverage but could not find a comprehensive data set.⁴ We also aimed to include more indicators on hospital size or the number of births per hospital to refine this geographic assessment, as hospital-level data is crucial when selecting target locations. Unfortunately, we could not find any such data. However, we emphasize that the most granular geographic assessments should ideally occur at the subnational or hospital level.

To maximize cost-effectiveness, an organization should likely prioritize large hospitals with high neonatal mortality rates, significant LBW prevalence, and care quality below conventional incubator standards. The specific country matters less than identifying these hospitals, so we recommend conducting in-country scoping in top-priority countries as soon as possible.

⁴ The best data we found was from a 2023 WHO report on KC implementation strategy. It reported the KC coverage in nine countries: Colombia (63%), the Philippines (53%), Ethiopia (46%), Bangladesh (22%), Malawi (22%), India (13%), Vietnam (8%), and subnational-level coverage in Rwanda (58% average across 10 districts) and Mali (41% average across three regions) ([World Health Organization, 2023](#)).

4 Updated evidence review

We reviewed new evidence since our 2022 analysis to evaluate how feasible it is for a charity to achieve impact in this space and the effectiveness of KC in reducing neonatal mortality and morbidity. Overall, we are encouraged by the early-stage success of Ansh, which demonstrates that a new charity can build strong relationships with key stakeholders critical for success (see [here](#)). Considering new evidence since publication, the mortality reduction effect of KC, initially thought to be 32%, now appears closer to ~25%, while the morbidity reduction effect, using sepsis as a proxy, has been updated from 15% to approximately 18%. We also evaluate how the duration of skin-to-skin contact could impact the effectiveness of KC.

4.1 Evidence that a charity can make a change in this space

Our original report relied on one case study of early success with the embedded capacity model implemented by a charity⁵: r.i.c.e's work in Uttar Pradesh. In Bahraich, r.i.c.e increased the number of KC-dedicated beds in a large hospital from 3 to 17 through facility investment and staffing increases. Since then, r.i.c.e has continued to operate its KC ward successfully, supervising 25–30 babies per day across these 17 beds. The program has also improved in quality and sustainability over time.

At the time, we were concerned that r.i.c.e's success might be overly context-dependent, relying heavily on their strong relationships with key stakeholders, such as a committed health ministry. While this remains a concern, Ansh appears to have also managed to overcome these challenges and is now scaling up KC through an embedded capacity model across Rajasthan. We are encouraged by Ansh's early-stage success, having supported 2,400 LBW babies

⁵ We also found observational data from a study detailing a successful government-led program in Bangladesh. Between 2016–2020, the program established new KC wards and training personnel, increasing the number of wards from 16 to 108. However, we remain uncertain about how much this government-led program informs the feasibility of success for a charity-led initiative.

and their families across two hospitals in Rajasthan in its pilot ([Bansal, 2024](#)). Encouragingly, Ansh has reduced the expected costs per baby by implementing a lighter-touch model than we initially envisioned. Rather than establishing new KC wards, they equip existing maternity wards with essentials like KC chairs, weighing scales, and KC wraps, while also providing training and staffing ([Bansal, 2024](#)). We see Ansh’s experience as a modest positive update on the feasibility of a new charity establishing and managing the stakeholder relationships necessary for successfully implementing this intervention.⁶

4.2 Evidence that the change has the expected health effects

We reviewed new evidence published since our 2022 investigation, focusing exclusively on meta-analyses and RCTs that evaluated mortality effects.

We found three new relevant studies, summarized alongside our key takeaways in Table 2.

Table 2: New meta-analyses and RCTs on KC with key takeaways

Study	Study methods and findings	Relevant update
Zhu et al. (2023)	A meta-analysis of 17 RCTs involving 17,668 participants concluded that KC “could reduce the primary clinical outcome of mortality between enrollment and 28 days (RR: 0.80, 95% CI: 0.71–0.91, $p < 0.01$). For secondary clinical outcomes, KC demonstrated varying degrees of benefits, including a reduction in the mean duration of hospital stay (SMD: -0.96 , 95% CI: -1.02 to -0.90 , $p < 0.001$), hypothermia (RR: 0.45, 95% CI: 0.27–0.75, $p < 0.01$), and sepsis (RR: 0.79, 95% CI: 0.70–0.89, $p < 0.001$)” compared to standard care (p.1)	This is a smaller reduction in mortality than we used in our previous cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) (32% previously vs. 20% in this meta-analysis), but a larger reduction in morbidity, where we used the reduction in the risk of sepsis as a proxy (15% previously vs. 21% from this meta-analysis).

⁶ We should note, however, that we are keen to see whether Ansh can achieve large-scale impact—and how quickly—and remain cautious about drawing broad conclusions given the venture’s start-up nature.

Study	Study methods and findings	Relevant update
Guo (2023)	A meta-analysis of 24 RCTs involving 19,980 participants (10,354 receiving KC and 9,626 under conventional care) concluded that KC “resulted in significantly lower mortality (OR: 0.65, 95% CI: 0.44–0.97, p = 0.03) in the short term (within 2 months, I ² = 71%) and long term (3–12 months) (OR: 0.72, 95% CI: 0.59–0.87, p = 0.0007, I ² = 0%), and had no significant impact on the length of hospital stay (OR: -1.43, 95% CI: -2.88–0.02, p = 0.05, I ² = 86%)” compared to conventional care (p.4).	This reduction in mortality is similar to the estimate we previously used (32%), with the meta-analysis suggesting a reduction of 35%.
Tumukunde et al. (2024)	An RCT conducted in five hospitals in Uganda compared KC (intervention group) to incubator or radiant heater care (control group). This study found that KC did not significantly reduce early neonatal mortality when compared to incubator or radiant heater care: “From randomization to age 7 days, 81 (7.5%) of 1,083 neonates in the intervention group and 83 (7.5%) of 1,102 neonates in the control group died (adjusted relative risk [RR] 0.97 [95% CI 0.74–1.28]; p=0.85). From randomization to 28 days, 119 (11.3%) of 1,051 neonates in the intervention group and 134 (12.8%) of 1,049 neonates in the control group died (RR 0.88 [0.71–1.09]; p=0.23).” (p.6) However, KC was found to be cheaper and more cost-effective than incubator care.	This result is somewhat confounding given other evidence, but we are not overly concerned as it suggests that KC is at least as effective as incubator care. Moreover, KC is best suited for settings where incubators are unavailable. It would have been more concerning if this study showed KC to be less effective than incubator care. We recommend targeting hospitals where incubators or radiant heaters are not the standard care.

This updated evidence review supports revising our model assumptions by lowering the expected reduction in mortality due to KC and increasing the expected reduction in morbidity. Previously, we relied on estimates from [Sivanandan and Sankar \(2023\)](#) which reported a 32% reduction in mortality and a 15% reduction in morbidity (using sepsis as a proxy). By taking a weighted average (weighted by sample size) of [Sivanandan and Sankar \(2023\)](#) and the three studies

outlined in Table 1, we now update these estimates to a 28% reduction in mortality and a 17% reduction in morbidity.

4.3 Duration of skin-to-skin contact per day

Many studies on KC assess its effectiveness based on 8 or more hours of daily skin-to-skin contact, alongside exclusive breastfeeding and close monitoring of the LBW neonate. However, it may be difficult to meet this contact duration while mothers are in the ward. During Ansh's pilot, mothers achieved only 4–5 hours per day ([Bansal, 2024](#)), though Supriya noted that this has since increased to 6–8 hours per day ([Bansal interview](#)). Adherence also tends to improve once mothers have been discharged, with 70% of mothers reaching at least 8 hours per day during the one-month follow-up period during their pilot ([Bansal, 2024](#)).

We evaluate how failing to meet 8 hours of daily skin-to-skin contact before discharge might impact this intervention's effectiveness. The World Health Organization recommends 8–24 hours of daily skin-to-skin contact for preterm or LBW babies but reports insufficient studies to evaluate the effectiveness of durations under 8 hours per day ([World Health Organization, 2022](#)). [Sivanandan and Sankar \(2023\)](#) similarly found that “there was insufficient data in the <8 hours group”. (p.11) [GiveWell](#) appears particularly concerned about skin-to-skin contact falling below 2 hours per day, noting that “KMC had no effect on mortality (18% increase, 95% CI = 68% decrease - 330% increase) in the subgroup of three studies [[from a 2016 Cochrane review](#)] in which the average duration of KMC was less than 2 hours/day”.

Due to a lack of evidence on the effect size of KC when less than 8 hours per day of skin-to-skin contact is given pre-discharge, we suggest discounting the number of babies receiving “optimal” KC by the percentage of babies receiving this duration in Ansh's pilot for our new cost-effectiveness analysis model. Notably, the studies we rely on report the effect size at 28 days of age, which coincides with the timing of Ansh's one-month follow-up. By then, 70% of mothers were achieving at least 8 hours of skin-to-skin contact daily in the pilot.

This could be an underestimate of the impact of this intervention if we expect there to still be similar mortality and morbidity reduction effects of skin-to-skin for durations less than 8 hours per day. We think that this could be plausible for two main reasons:

1. KC is made up of components other than skin-to-skin contact: exclusive breastfeeding and close monitoring of the baby. These components are equally important, so if they are still being done then we may be less concerned about durations of skin-to-skin contact of under 8 hours per day.
2. Babies will likely still receive more than 2 hours per day of skin-to-skin contact, which was the duration under which [GiveWell](#) seemed most concerned about having no mortality effects. Therefore, it may be more accurate to discount the impacts of KC by the percentage of babies receiving less than 2 hours per day of skin-to-skin contact only, not those receiving less than 8 hours per day.

5 Expert views

5.1 Supriya Bansal, Ansh

Supriya was excited about us recommending another KC non-profit. She shared that Ansh is currently scaling in Rajasthan and plans to expand across India and would prefer the new charity to focus on a different country, highlighting Pakistan and Nigeria as particularly promising options. When choosing a target country, Supriya highlighted the difficulty in finding hospitals where you can reach 1,200+ low birth weight and premature babies. She thought that this could be a challenge in countries not as heavily populated as India. Ansh currently works in one of the biggest states in the most populated country in the world which enables them to reach an average of 1,200 babies per hospital.

While Supriya was not concerned about funding cannibalization, she raised some concerns about reputational risks if the new charity is too closely associated with Ansh and fails or makes mistakes. She believed this risk would likely be limited if the new organization operated in a different country (outside India). However, she was worried that such a failure could lead to undue skepticism about the effectiveness of KC as an intervention. She described this concern as minor and noted that it shouldn't be a barrier to us starting a new charity.

Supriya emphasized that managing stakeholder relationships has been key to Ansh's success. She believes having a local co-founder is essential for building strong relationships and gaining full access to hospitals, governments, and nurses. She highlighted that speaking the local language and not being seen as an outsider is important—Ansh faced challenges, for instance, when non-Indian people tried to access government hospitals during their pilot. Supriya also expressed greater concern about reputational risks if the new charity were to launch with two foreign co-founders.

On founder requirements, Supriya also highlighted that she doesn't think it is particularly relevant or necessary for the founding team to have a healthcare/medical background to start a KC charity. KC itself isn't highly

technical, and Ansh's approach follows a light-touch model within existing hospitals, where the hospital's doctors remain the primary decision-makers for the babies (and she would recommend that a new organization take a similar light-touch model for cost-effectiveness and sustainability). Moreover, founders are not going to be training parents to do KC themselves. They will hire staff (likely local healthcare workers) to do this, who will be trained due healthcare professionals.

She also highlighted the importance of the broader package of neonatal interventions within KC, beyond just skin-to-skin contact, in driving the mortality reductions observed in Ansh's work. In particular, they also counsel parents to recognize danger signs in their babies, such as symptoms of acute respiratory distress, so parents know when to return to the hospital for emergency care. She speculated that this monitoring component may be the component that contributes most to the mortality reductions Ansh has seen. Note that this component needs to be tailored to the specific context of the hospitals the non-profit works in.

We also asked Supriya why parents in their pilot were unable to meet the recommended 8 hours of skin-to-skin contact when they were on the ward. Supriya noted that they have since managed to increase the average duration from 4–5 hours during their pilot to 6–8 hours during their scale-up phase, and they have two upcoming research studies where they will be experimenting with ways to increase this even further. Supriya also noted a distinction between stable and unstable babies: stable babies are quickly discharged, and over 70% of parents reported consistently achieving 8 or more hours of skin-to-skin contact daily at home during follow-ups in the pilot. Unstable babies require additional tests and treatment, meaning they spend more time away from their mothers and under medical care. In such cases, skin-to-skin contact is limited by doctors' recommendations. Therefore, if doctors suggest only 4 hours of skin-to-skin contact, parents adhere to that limit. She emphasized the need to interpret average pre-discharge skin-to-skin contact duration within this context.

5.2 Meika Ball, GiveWell

Meika thinks that embedding capacity in the health system and community initiation of KC through health workers are both promising ToCs, though there is slightly more evidence supporting the embedding capacity model, based on existing studies and organizations. She noted that community initiation might have greater impact on individual babies compared to facility-based KC as the counterfactual care for babies outside hospitals is likely much worse, and the support period in community-based KC could be significantly longer. Meika suggested that prioritizing community initiation of KC would be more appropriate in the following situations:

- When hospitals are operating beyond capacity, making it impossible to embed capacity due to space constraints.
- When the rate of births happening in facilities is generally low
- Where community health worker platforms are already robust and the primary form of care, e.g., in countries where most antenatal care is provided by community health workers.

Meika believes there is room for a new organization to focus on facility-based KC but notes that while few organizations focus exclusively on KC, some may already be promoting it as part of a broader program. For example, Population Services International is active in facilities and neonatal wards, where KC might be one of several interventions included in their work.

We also discussed the evidence base for facility-based KC. GiveWell is currently relying on [Sivanandan and Sankar \(2023\)](#), though Meika highlighted some concerns with this meta-analysis. The most significant concern is that the study with the highest weighting ([Mazumder et al., 2019](#)) evaluated community-based KC rather than facility-based KC.

6 Updated cost-effectiveness analysis

We updated our 2022 cost-effectiveness analysis using our new template, incorporating updated cost and reach data from Ansh's pilot and revised effect sizes for KC's impact on mortality and morbidity based on our latest evidence review. Embedding KC capacity in hospitals in Pakistan is expected to be highly cost-effective. The updated model estimates that the intervention could avert one DALY for every \$50 spent or 20 DALYs per \$1,000 spent.

Our [updated cost-effectiveness analysis model](#) uses our new cost-effectiveness analysis template to model a potential new charity embedding KC capacity into existing hospitals in Pakistan. The model assumes a lighter-touch intervention compared to our initial analysis, replicating Ansh's approach of embedding capacity into existing maternity wards rather than establishing new dedicated KC wards. This involves providing KC chairs, wraps, backrests, weighing scales, training, and resources for hiring, facility management, and monitoring and evaluation. Where appropriate, we rely on cost, reach, and adherence data from Ansh's pilot to inform the model. **We note that this model relies on pilot data based on work in two hospitals in Rajasthan from January-March 2024, but Ansh is now in their scale-up phase so specific numbers used in this model could already be out of date.**

Embedding KC capacity in hospitals in Pakistan is expected to be highly cost-effective. Assuming the charity can scale to 15 hospitals per year, reaching 1,200 babies per hospital, the model estimates the intervention could avert one DALY for every \$50 spent or 20 DALYs per \$1,000 spent (Table 3).

Table 3: Cost-effectiveness of embedding KC capacity into hospitals in Pakistan

	Pakistan
Total number of people reached	176,400
Total DALYs averted	214,274
Total costs	\$10,754,794

	Pakistan
Cost-effectiveness (\$/DALY)	\$50
Cost-effectiveness (DALY/\$1000)	20

We note that this cost-effectiveness estimate may underestimate the intervention's effectiveness for three main reasons:

1. We have assumed that not reaching 8 hours of skin-to-skin contact impacts the overall effectiveness of KC. This could be overly cautious, as discussed in [Section 4.3](#).
2. It does not account for the potential cost savings to hospitals due to KC reducing the time babies spend in care.
3. KC is cheaper than alternative treatments, such as incubator care, which has not been factored into this analysis.

6.1 Effects

We calculated the net present value benefits for the intervention by applying the following discounts:

- A standard annual discount of 1.4%.
- A 7.7% annual discount to account for current expected KC coverage.

There were two main benefits we quantified in the model:

1. Mortality reduction: Calculated by taking the expected baseline neonatal mortality rate and applying the expected ~29.3% mortality reduction due to KC.⁷ This was then multiplied by the expected DALY benefit of saving the neonate's life.
2. Morbidity reduction: Focused on the impact of KC on sepsis as a proxy for the morbidity impacts. This was calculated by applying the expected ~17.3%

⁷ We took a weighted average (weighted by sample size) of the effect sizes from the three studies evaluated in our updated evidence review and the meta-analysis relied upon in our previous cost-effectiveness analysis. This calculation resulted in a mortality reduction estimate of 28.1%. We then applied internal and externality validity adjustments to refine this estimate.

morbidity reduction⁸ due to KC by the expected DALY benefit associated with reduced morbidity and developmental effects of being LBW.

- a. Since no direct estimates of the DALY benefits were available, these were calculated by multiplying the disability weight for being LBW by the life expectancy in Pakistan.

6.2 Costs

The model assumes the charity would have about four full-time staff members, with fixed costs estimated at \$280,000 at scale. This fixed cost estimate is usually held constant between all of our cost-effectiveness analysis models.

For variable costs, we used data from Ansh's pilot ([Bansal, 2024](#)):

- Equipment and training setup costs of \$4,500 per hospital, where we assume these items last for three years.
- Hiring and facility management costs of \$60,000 per hospital per year.
- Monitoring and evaluation costs of \$7,200 per hospital per year.

This results in variable costs of ~\$57 per baby per year.

We calculated the net present value of these costs using a standard 4% annual discount.

6.3 Reach

We calculate the reach of this intervention by multiplying the following factors:

- Number of babies reached per hospital: 1,200, based on Ansh's pilot ([Bansal, 2024](#))
 - Supriya highlighted the difficulty in finding hospitals where you can reach 1,200+ low birth weight and premature babies. She thought that this could be a challenge in countries not as heavily populated as India. Ansh currently works in one of the biggest states in the most

⁸ We took a weighted average (weighted by sample size) of the effect sizes from [Sivanandan and Sankar \(2023\)](#) and [Zhu et al. \(2023\)](#) to estimate a morbidity reduction of 17% compared to conventional care. We then applied internal and externality validity adjustments to refine this estimate.

populated country in the world which enables them to reach an average of 1,200 babies per hospital.

- Number of hospitals reached at scale: 15
- Expected adherence to skin-to-skin contact for more than or equal to 8 hours per day: 70%, as this was the proportion of mothers who achieved this duration at their one-month follow-up in Ansh’s pilot ([Bansal, 2024](#)).

6.4 External cost-effectiveness estimates

Several external cost-effectiveness estimates have been developed to model the impact of KC interventions. These estimates are outlined in Table 4.

Table 4: External cost-effectiveness estimates on KC interventions

Author	What is being modeled?	Cost-effectiveness estimate
GiveWell (2021)	A program expanding KC throughout hospitals as described in Broughton et al. (2013)	\$1,485–3,714 per neonatal death averted
Spears (2022)	r.i.c.e’s KC program in Uttar Pradesh, India, embedding KC capacity into hospitals	~\$2,000–3,000 per neonatal death averted
Bansal (2024)	Ansh’s pilot in Rajasthan, India, embedding KC capacity into hospitals (lighter-touch model)	\$2,077 per neonatal death averted

6.5 Comparison to previous cost-effectiveness analysis

We compare the most significant parameters in our new cost-effectiveness model and our [2022 cost-effectiveness analysis](#) in Table 5. Both models use a similar methodology, but in our updated model we use our new cost-effectiveness analysis template and some updated numbers.

Table 5: Comparison to previous cost-effectiveness analysis

Parameter	New model	Old model (2022)	Reason for difference
Geographic focus	Pakistan	Pakistan	N/A
Cost per LBW infant	\$57	\$264.48	We now use cost estimates from Ansh's pilot, which adopts a lighter-touch approach compared to the previous model (providing KC equipment and training vs. establishing dedicated wards).
Mortality reduction effect due to KC (before internal and external validity adjustments)	28.1%	32%	We now use a weighted average (weighted by sample size) of effect sizes from four studies, three of which were published after our previous 2022 analysis. In our old model, we just relied on Sivanandan and Sankar (2023) . We now also apply internal (-10%) and external (+30%) validity adjustments to this estimate where we didn't previously.
Morbidity reduction effect due to KC (before internal and external validity adjustments)	17%	15%	We now use a weighted average (weighted by sample size) of effect sizes from two studies, one of which was published after our previous 2022 analysis. In our old model, we just relied on Sivanandan and Sankar (2023) . We now also apply internal (-10%) and external (+30%) validity adjustments to this estimate where we didn't previously.
Probability of success	70%	65%	We positively updated on the expected probability of success based on the early successes of Ansh.
Total number of people reached	176,400	51,639	We now rely on data from Ansh's pilot on the number of LBW infants reached per hospital. Based on our conversations with implementers, we now assume a charity could scale to 15 hospitals instead of 4 as previously modeled.

Parameter	New model	Old model (2022)	Reason for difference
Total DALYs averted	214,274	110,183	This reflects the revised model parameters outlined above.
Total costs	~\$10.8M	~\$10.8M	Interestingly, the overall costs remain similar across the two models, despite their differences, as the new model reaches more people at a lower cost per individual.
Cost-effectiveness (\$/DALY)	\$50	\$98	This reflects the revised model parameters outlined above.
Cost-effectiveness (DALY/\$1000)	20	10.22	This reflects the revised model parameters outlined above.

7 Implementation

7.1 Talent

Supriya noted concerns about reputational risk and efficiency if a new charity is launched without a local co-founder. She emphasized that having a local founder would provide significant benefits, particularly in building strong stakeholder relationships—a key component of this intervention. Hospitals often prefer engaging directly with the organization’s leaders, so being able to speak the local language and avoid being perceived as an outsider would be beneficial ([Bansal interview](#)). Additionally, a local founder may have easier access to hospitals, the government, and healthcare staff.

We also believe that it would benefit the founding team to have a healthcare/medical background and that excellent stakeholder management skills will be essential in the team. Supriya also highlighted the importance of stakeholder management, but does not believe that a healthcare/medical background is particularly relevant or necessary to start a KC charity ([Bansal interview](#)).

References

- Bansal, S. (2024). Introducing Ansh: A Charity Entrepreneurship Incubated Charity. <https://forum.effectivealtruism.org/posts/hTEaKau8D4Ah3NPcu/introducing-ansh-a-charity-entrepreneurship-incubated>
- Broughton, E. I., Gomez, I., Sanchez, N., & Vindell, C. (2013). The cost-savings of implementing kangaroo mother care in Nicaragua. *Rev Panam Salud Publica*, 34(3), 176-82. <https://scielosp.org/pdf/rpsp/2013.v34n3/176-182/en>
- Conde-Agudelo, . & Diaz-Rossello. (2016). Kangaroo mother care to reduce morbidity and mortality in low birthweight infants. *Cochrane Library*. <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD002771.pub4/full>
- Fairless, M. (2022). Scaling up kangaroo care for low birth weight babies. *Ambitious Impact*. https://9475dbf4-555e-4808-9886-5f8ee815cc82.usrfiles.com/ugd/9475db_36299f8b6e344077b3630e2aa786c03a.pdf
- GiveWell. (2021, February). Kangaroo Mother Care. *GiveWell*. <https://www.givewell.org/international/technical/programs/kangaroo-mother-care>
- Guo, W. (2023) Evaluation of the impact of kangaroo mother care on neonatal mortality and hospitalization: A meta-analysis. *Adv Clin Exp Med*, 32(2), 175-183. <https://advances.umw.edu.pl/en/article/2023/32/2/175/>
- Mazumder, S. et al. (2019). Effect of community-initiated kangaroo mother care on survival of infants with low birthweight: a randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 394(10210), 1724-1736. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31590989/>
- Nimbalkar, S., Popat, V., Patel, P., Pujara, R., Shinde, M., & Patel, D. (2023). Effect of Kangaroo Mother Care Transport in Preventing Moderate Hypothermia in Low Birth Weight Babies During Transportation to Home After Discharge: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Indian Pediatrics*, 60(4), 272-276. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36757001/>
- Okwaraji, Y. B., et al. (2024). National, regional, and global estimates of low birthweight in 2020, with trends from 2000: a systematic analysis. *The Lancet*, 403(10431), 1071-1080. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(23\)01198-4](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(23)01198-4)
- Sivanandan, S. & Sankar, M. J. (2023). Kangaroo mother care for preterm or low birth weight infants: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Global Health*, 8. <https://gh.bmj.com/content/8/6/e010728>
- Sloan, N. L., Camacho, L. W., Rojas, E. P., & Stern, C. (1994). Kangaroo mother

- method: randomised controlled trial of an alternative method of care for stabilised low-birthweight infants. Maternidad Isidro Ayora Study Team. *The Lancet*, 344(8925), 782-785. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7916073/>
- Sloan, N. L., Ahmed, S., Mitra, S. N., Choudhury, N., Chowdhury, M., Rob, U., & Winikoff, B. (2008). Community-Based Kangaroo Mother Care to Prevent Neonatal and Infant Mortality: A Randomized, Controlled Cluster Trial. *Pediatrics*, 121(5), 1047-1059. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2007-0076>
- Sontheimer, D., Fischer, C. B., & Buch, K. E. (2004). Kangaroo Transport Instead of Incubator Transport. *Pediatrics*, 113(4). <https://healthynewbornnetwork.org/hnn-content/uploads/KMC-transport.pdf>
- Spears, D. (2022). r.i.c.e.'s neonatal lifesaving partnership is funded by GiveWell; a description of what we do. <https://forum.effectivealtruism.org/posts/8CRFTxrRLiizypyBu/r-i-c-e-s-neonatal-lifesaving-partnership-is-funded-by>
- Tumukunde, V., et al. (2024). Effectiveness of kangaroo mother care before clinical stabilisation versus standard care among neonates at five hospitals in Uganda (OMWaNA): a parallel-group, individually randomised controlled trial and economic evaluation. *The Lancet*, 403(10443), 2520-2532. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(24\)00064-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(24)00064-3)
- Whitelaw, A., Heisterkamp, G., Sleath, K., Acolet, D., & Richards, M. (1998). Skin to skin contact for very low birthweight infants and their mothers. <https://doi.org/10.1136/adc.63.11.1377>
- World Health Organization. (2022). WHO recommendations for care of the preterm or low-birth-weight infant. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/363697/9789240058262-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
- World Health Organization. (2023). Kangaroo mother care: implementation strategy for scale-up adaptable to different country contexts. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/367625/9789240071636-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Zhu, Z., Wang, X., Chen, W., Pei, S., Wang, Q., Guan, H., & Zhu, G. (2023). The efficacy of Kangaroo-Mother care to the clinical outcomes of LBW and premature infants in the first 28 days: A meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *Front. Pediatr.*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2023.1067183>